

WORKSHOP

21 Maio 2025, Algés - Portugal

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR A MORE COMPETITIVE NATIONAL AQUACULTURE

Topics

Artificial intelligence
Functional feeds
Food safety
Animal welfare

SESSION RESULTS

This document results from a workshop that brought together stakeholders from the national aquaculture sector to reflect on the future of the sector until 2035. The discussion focused on identifying the main threats and challenges, strengths and opportunities, and the needs for research and development (R&D) and regulation.

The objective of this initiative was to build a comprehensive and realistic overview, mapping gaps and priorities that will enable strengthening the sector and making it more sustainable, resilient, and competitive.

The document is structured into four areas – threats/challenges, strengths/opportunities, R&D needs, and regulatory needs – reflecting the ideas and contributions shared during the session and serving as a basis for future strategies in the development of national aquaculture.

We thank all participants who shared their perspectives, knowledge, and experience, essential for the quality and depth of this collective reflection

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The participants noted that the two presented scenarios are extreme and do not fully reflect reality. However, this choice was deliberate, as the objective was precisely to clearly highlight both the advantages and the obstacles associated with a scenario based on sustainability and technological innovation, as well as a scenario grounded in liberalization and globalization. In practice, regulation can adopt divergent approaches, even on very similar topics, and therefore, projecting opposite and extreme scenarios allows for the exploration of these possibilities. In the end, the information gathered by the participants for both scenarios was combined in each of the sessions to present a balanced perspective that emphasized the opportunities and limitations of these extreme scenarios projected for 2035.

Weaknesses and threats to the competitiveness of national aquaculture

Artificial intelligence

- The regulation of AI use is still unclear and lacks transparency.
- The validation of AI tools often occurs in controlled or pilot environments, without effective planning to transfer these tests to real contexts and at scale. This hinders the consolidation of solutions in the production sector.
- The absence of clear open data policies makes it difficult to access the information necessary to train robust AI models. The lack of interoperability and data sharing between public entities, private companies, and research centres limits the advancement of AI tool usage.
- Dependence on public support, which can be unstable or conditioned by political cycles, raises doubts about the sustainability of AI investments. The absence of a national strategy may mean funding will rely mainly on private initiatives.
- Excessive use of automated systems can lead to the loss of critical capacity among sector professionals, replacing human knowledge with decisions based solely on algorithms.
- Cybersecurity represents a growing threat, especially considering the volume and sensitivity of the data involved. Poorly protected systems are vulnerable to attacks, manipulations, or leaks, compromising trust and system integrity.
- The scarcity of highly qualified human resources in AI, especially with knowledge applied to aquaculture, is a significant obstacle. Companies face difficulties both recruiting and retaining talent.
- The proliferation of misinformation and the use of AI to generate false content (fake news) create uncertainties about the reliability of digital solutions. Moreover, there is a lack of clarity about how AI can be used ethically to combat this misinformation.
- The environmental impact associated with AI use, particularly in terms of energy and water consumption by data centres, may contradict sustainability goals.
- Companies, especially SMEs, face high costs to acquire, adapt, and integrate AI and machine learning tools, hindering the democratization of these technologies.
- Private investment capital tends to be volatile and driven by short-term interests, which compromises the stability necessary for the development of AI solutions that require time and continuity.
- There is a lack of investors with specific interest in applying AI to aquaculture, especially regarding small-scale production.

- The transition from proof of concept to scaled production presents technical, operational, and financial difficulties. Without public support or strategic partnerships, many innovations fail to be implemented.
- A liberal context may further accentuate inequalities between large producers and SMEs. Companies with greater investment capacity will be able to apply AI more effectively, expanding their competitive advantage.
- Reduced control and monitoring may compromise food safety and weaken consumer confidence.
- The development of AI solutions tends to be oriented toward the interests of large multinational companies, leaving out the specific needs of local producers.
- AI can be irresponsibly used to promote sustainability claims without scientific basis (greenwashing), confusing consumers and harming producers who follow good practices.
- SMEs face major difficulties implementing AI solutions due to high costs and a shortage of qualified professionals, who tend to be absorbed by large companies.
- Excessive data protection and intellectual property rights hinder the development of collaborative and open tools.

functional feeds

- There is a need to increase the production scale of the sector (upscale) in a planned, effective, efficient, and sustainable manner.
- Existing regulatory barriers relate to: 1) the use of maritime space for aquaculture facilities; and 2) the approval of new ingredients and additives in feed.
- The use of functional feeds/ingredients will naturally represent an increase in production costs, which in turn will be reflected in the value of the marketed fish. Thus, the introduction of more expensive products to the market will face enormous challenges, mainly due to large distribution networks that promote the consumption of “low-cost” aquaculture fish coming from countries where sustainability, animal welfare, and food safety standards are substantially lower.
- Lower regulatory barriers in third countries regarding the use of raw materials for feed production may foster “unfair competition,” allowing the entry into the European market of products with much lower production costs, making “premium” aquaculture fish (produced with more sustainable and/or functional feeds) less attractive and accessible to consumers.
- The use of functional feeds should imply the creation of labels certifying safety, sustainability, and respect for animal welfare, which will in turn also represent increased production costs.
- Creating market niches for “premium” fish produced with these new feeds is a necessary action.
- Functional feeds, being more expensive, will be inaccessible to most producers, particularly SMEs, who are already operating at the limits of their investment capacity.
- There is resistance from producers regarding the introduction of new technologies and raw materials, due to a preference for traditional production processes. This resistance may be due to higher costs or distrust regarding the use of new technologies.
- There is a need to develop nutrition studies to improve knowledge about the acceptance of feeds with new formulations by species relevant to aquaculture.

- There is a lack of knowledge about the efficiency and effectiveness of nutrient and bioactive compound utilization/metabolization by the produced species.
- With a greater number of companies producing and lower regulatory requirements, it is likely that production costs will decrease and competition will increase. As a consequence, prices tend to drop, reducing companies' profit margins, which could weaken the sector if unexpected changes arise.
- Profit reduction and regulation could compromise animal welfare, with potential impacts on public health.
- There is a growing tendency among students to move away from production-related fields, particularly aquaculture, resulting in a shortage of specialized human resources with the necessary knowledge and experience to face the sector's specific challenges.
- The absence of investment in the development of functional feeds will favour feeds with traditional formulations (higher percentages of fish protein and oil), whose scarcity could lead to uncertainties and increased costs of raw materials.
- Portuguese consumers are not sensitized to value the increased production cost of higher-quality products.
- There is a heavy dependence on and use of imported raw materials at low prices, often with limited inspection, high ecological footprint, lower quality standards, and less sustainability.

food safety

- Climate change represents a significant threat to food security in the aquaculture sector, since it directly impacts the environmental conditions essential for fish production. Rising water temperatures, marine acidification, the occurrence of extreme weather events (such as heatwaves), and hypoxia compromise the health, growth, and survival of farmed species. Furthermore, these changes favour the proliferation of diseases and the introduction of invasive species, affecting water quality and food chain safety.
- Emerging risks such as microplastics, antibiotic residues, parasites, toxins, pathogenic bacteria, and viruses pose a growing threat to consumers. These agents can harm the health of farmed organisms, reduce the quality and safety of final products, and raise public health concerns.
- Challenges related to maritime conditions and sea access may threaten the food security of aquaculture products, as the predictability of production and the integrity of infrastructures (e.g., cages, nets, sensors) may be compromised due to the increased frequency and intensity of extreme events such as storms and changes in ocean currents. Additionally, growing competition for the use of marine space (e.g., due to tourism) may limit aquaculture expansion, requiring more efficient zoning and integrated management policies to ensure safe and sustainable access to coastal and offshore areas.
- A lack of in-depth knowledge about markets and consumer behaviour may pose a threat to food security. Unawareness of preferences, consumption habits, nutritional requirements, and sustainability concerns may lead to economic losses for producers, limiting the sector's capacity to adapt and innovate. Market trends and trade barriers may also hinder the population's access to quality, safe, and affordable products.
- Ineffective communication, marked by misinformation and a lack of public trust, represents a relevant challenge for food security, as it may compromise access, acceptance, and proper

use of aquaculture products. Moreover, it may hinder the implementation of traceability systems, which are crucial to ensuring confidence and sanitary control.

- Increasing dependence on technologies may become a threat to food security, as production relies heavily on sensors, artificial intelligence, and automation, making the sector vulnerable to technical failures and cyberattacks. Failures in these systems may compromise environmental control, feeding, organism health, and traceability, directly affecting product quality, availability, and safety for the population.
- External dependence on raw materials, such as feed ingredients, constitutes a threat to food security, making the sector vulnerable to fluctuations in international markets, supply chain disruptions, cost increases, and geopolitical instabilities. Production may be affected, and final products may become more expensive, hindering availability and accessibility for the population and leading to food insecurity.
- Production costs may rise due to investments in advanced technologies, certifications, and sustainable production practices, which on the one hand will bring benefits but on the other will make products more expensive and less accessible to some population segments, potentially causing social and economic inequalities in the sector and compromising product quality and safety.
- A lack of efficient organization in the sector may hinder adaptation to regulations and rapid response capacity to new challenges, even if compliance is supervised by autonomous entities.
- Geopolitical instability is a significant threat that greatly, though indirectly, affects the entire value chain, from producers to consumers. International conflicts, trade sanctions, or territorial disputes may interrupt the supply of essential materials, such as feed, and hinder market access. Thus, geopolitical instability may weaken continuous and secure access to aquaculture products, directly impacting food availability and accessibility for the human population.
- Diversifying aquaculture production requires prior risk assessment associated with recognizing new species as suitable for human consumption, as required by entities such as DGAV (Directorate-General for Food and Veterinary) and ASAE (Authority for Economic and Food Safety). While such introduction may offer opportunities for diversification and innovation, it also poses food security challenges, especially when gaps remain in knowledge about the ecological, nutritional, and sanitary needs of these species.
- The One Health concept – Environmental, Animal, and Human – is an essential approach to promote food security. When effectively applied in aquaculture, it can help prevent ecological imbalances, reduce the spread of pathogenic microorganisms, minimize excessive antimicrobial use, and avoid water contamination. This will protect ecosystems, farmed organisms, and human population health.
- Increased costs associated with innovation, effluent treatment, and infrastructure maintenance, especially in RAS production systems (Recirculating Aquaculture Systems).
- Decrease in qualified human resources to ensure compliance with the analytical complexity involved in food safety.
- Increase in misinformation and misleading marketing in the aquaculture sector, including cases of “greenwashing,” where companies or institutions promote initiatives, products, or

Challenges and opportunities for a more competitive Portuguese aquaculture

practices as sustainable or environmentally responsible without evidence or concrete actions to support these claims.

- Decrease in the diversification of produced species, making consumer acceptance of these products more difficult.

animal welfare

- Although the producer has the greatest interest in adopting good animal welfare practices, these are not always economically viable, and their enforcement may make the activity unsustainable for small producers. An example of this is stunning equipment used offshore, whose high investment cost is not feasible for small offshore producers.
- Regulation to ensure animal welfare entails high costs for national producers, but results in a higher-quality product. The entry of products from countries with less stringent welfare standards, which allows them to offer more competitive prices, creates unfair competition that threatens the economic viability of the national sector. This competition compromises the economic feasibility of implementing high animal welfare standards at the national level.
- Most aquaculture producers have training in veterinary sciences and possess high knowledge and skills to prevent, manage, and treat diseases. New regulations require that medicinal mixtures be produced only by accredited entities, underutilizing the practical knowledge acquired by these professionals through direct contact with production processes (see regulatory needs).
- Increased risk of uncontrolled use of antibiotics, biocides, and other chemicals, leading to exacerbated microbial resistance.
- Lack of regulation may lead to intensive practices that negatively impact mortality, animal welfare, and the quality of the final product.
- Portugal's network of urban wastewater treatment plants is undersized for current population densities, causing significant environmental impacts and increasing risks for aquatic animal producers, especially bivalve farmers, given the correlation between poor water sanitation and high mortality rates.

Strengths and opportunities for a more competitive aquaculture

artificial intelligence

- AI can help demystify negative perceptions about aquaculture and its products, increasing consumer confidence through greater traceability and transparency in production processes.
- Traceability, facilitated by AI-based systems, strengthens food safety and has the potential to increase the market value of aquaculture products. New AI tools can guarantee product authenticity and traceability, boosting consumer trust in these products.
- AI enables real-time analysis of environmental and operational variables, optimizing production and reducing costs. Data-driven decision-making can also anticipate risks and minimize losses.
- Animal welfare can be promoted through intelligent monitoring systems that detect early and automatically signs of stress, disease, or behavioural changes, allowing faster and less invasive interventions.

Challenges and opportunities for a more competitive Portuguese aquaculture

- Investing in training professionals in AI applied to aquaculture boosts sector qualification and increases its international competitiveness.
- Technology development focused on sector challenges enables more personalized and effective solutions, strengthening national innovation and attracting external investment.
- In a context with lower AI adoption, human knowledge remains central, which can favour job retention, although often with lower wages.
- Reduced investment in AI technologies can translate into lower production costs and more affordable aquaculture product prices for consumers, albeit with increased challenges in quality and traceability.
- A lower level of technological sophistication can facilitate mass production through simpler, standardized processes less dependent on large investments.
- The private sector can lead applied research focused on immediate results and incremental innovation.
- Encouraging the creation of public-private partnerships brings scientific research closer to business reality, fostering practical innovation with faster returns.

functional feeds

- Improve the business organization of the sector to allow for upscale production.
- Invest in installing land-based RAS systems, focusing on smaller units deployed in greater numbers to help mitigate risks inherent to climate events, disease outbreaks, and scarcity of natural resources (water, energy, etc.).
- Invest in diversifying the species produced and introducing new products to the market, different from those currently available, to overcome unfair competition from low-cost fish produced in third countries.
- Focus on functionality for human nutrition through the development of new products that address nutritional deficiencies in different population segments.
- Invest in bioprospection of new ingredients/additives (e.g., pigments) that provide unique and/or improved organoleptic characteristics to the fish.
- Valorisation of by-products through the promotion of circular economy and zero waste, allowing the development of new products at accessible costs.
- Improve the management of farmed animals by training producers so they can maximize production in line with sustainability and animal welfare principles, and accept new technologies.
- Promote the value of functional fish (produced or enriched to offer additional health benefits) and sustainable fish, ensuring consumer acceptance through the creation of labels that certify all product quality and safety criteria, although with increased costs.
- Reduced regulation combined with greater availability of land use could lead to increased production scale, with greater efficiency, effectiveness in production, and better sales opportunities (lower prices without reducing profit).
- Incentives or tax benefits may arise to attract new producers in response to the need to increase production.
- Diversify production focusing on products such as algae, aiming to exploit still underdeveloped markets. Production can target both exports—especially to countries where

consumption of these products is habitual—and the domestic market, promoting their use as ingredients, particularly in vegetarian and vegan recipes.

- Reduced regulation could facilitate the exploitation of new business opportunities, increasing market size and sales opportunities.
- Companies with greater financial resources invest part of their profits in research and development of more innovative and technological solutions and/or products (see R&D needs).
- Specialized feed-producing companies may focus on niche and/or more specialized markets, reducing the potential impacts related to lack of investment in R&D.
- Greater incentives for short supply chains through increased investment in promoting the consumption of local products among consumers, through collaborations between producers and the hotel/restaurant industry.
- Promote to consumers the importance of consuming aquaculture products both nutritionally and in terms of economic and environmental sustainability, through collaborations with the hotel/restaurant sector in developing and promoting new recipes and/or cooking methods that favor their consumption.
- Increase the use of aquaculture by-products for the development of new products, for human consumption or other industries (e.g., cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and animal feed).

food safety

- The harmonization of technologies in aquaculture can represent a great opportunity to strengthen food security, since the integration of traceability systems based on sensors, artificial intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Things (IoT) allows real-time monitoring of all production stages, ensuring greater transparency, better sanitary control, and a rapid response to incidents. In this way, it is possible to detect and identify failures early, prevent risks, and ensure that products reach consumers with quality and safety.
- Transparent and effective communication through apps and digital platforms, combined with the promotion of multigenerational and multisectorial literacy, emerges as a strategic opportunity to reinforce food security. These tools facilitate information sharing among producers, consumers, researchers, and policymakers, promoting transparency, traceability, and trust in products. The dissemination of information on sustainability, food safety, and nutritional value to diverse audiences encourages more conscious consumption choices and more responsible production practices.
- The existence of effective contingency plans along the value chain strengthens food security by enabling rapid responses to incidents (such as disease outbreaks, logistical failures, or extreme climate events), ensuring the continuity of production, product quality, and consumer confidence.
- Compliance with more requirements for safety, product quality, and sustainability strengthens trust in the sector, guarantees safe products, and facilitates market access, contributing to safer and more resilient aquaculture.
- The use of alternative raw materials and ingredients, such as plant-based proteins, reduces dependence on traditional resources like fishmeal and fish oil, making production more sustainable and contributing to the production of safe and nutritious food. The greater availability of these raw materials will also allow increased food supply. Furthermore, the

adoption of emerging technologies and new raw materials can reduce production costs, which can make the sector more competitive and its products more accessible.

- The development of innovative production systems, such as land-based aquaculture, increases environmental and sanitary control (including water quality management), guaranteeing safer products.
- The diversification and introduction of new species in national aquaculture production, such as algae, promote more efficient use of resources, reduce waste, and favour circular and complementary systems. Additionally, it increases production sustainability and the variety of available products, contributing to more robust food security with diversified and nutritious products.
- The holistic One Health approach, which integrates the health of the environment, animals, and humans, strengthens food security because it helps prevent diseases, reduce antimicrobial use, and minimize environmental impacts, thereby ensuring safer, quality, sustainable products beneficial to public health.
- Reduced sector regulation may facilitate easier creation of production infrastructures and foster new business opportunities.

animal welfare

- Appropriate and well-applied regulation on animal welfare and environmental impact creates opportunities to generate value through animal welfare and environmental certifications. These certifications could contribute to better product acceptance and greater consumer trust, particularly if complemented by traceability tools. To be effective, they must be accompanied by awareness campaigns about the importance of ensuring animal welfare and environmental sustainability to prevent resource waste and promote responsible practices. This certification would add value to national products and recognize producers' efforts to make the product safer, more sustainable, and ensure good animal welfare conditions.
- Securing funding to support public communication about the quality of national and include schools in demonstration activities, which would help make aquaculture production more accepted by the population.
- Provision of funding to ensure the exchange of academic personnel with the national production system to improve communication between sectors and foster applied research focused on problem-solving.
- Implementation and awareness of the One Health concept in national aquaculture.
- Increase in production and density per production area with value-added products, allowing aquaculturist to increase their income and enhance the value of their products to consumers.
- Reduction of operational costs through infrastructure modernization, namely optimizing feed consumption monitoring and implementing AI tools.
- Specialized technical training, enhancing job quality.
- Creation and strengthening of synergies between entities such as the Portuguese Association of aquaculturists, producers, and sellers, aimed at energizing consumption marketing strategies and demystifying aquaculture products.

Challenges and opportunities for a more competitive Portuguese aquaculture

- Implementation of a quality certification system based on a product specification/history, with the creation of a welfare label or seal indicating origin, traceability, and type of production (e.g., intensive/semi-intensive).
- Implementation of standardized audits to ensure effective and constructive supervision in national aquaculture.
- Implementation of environmental impact mitigation measures combined with the simplification of regulatory barriers.
- Use of mathematical models (machine learning) and non-invasive methods (sensors and AI) to anticipate, *in silico*, potential phenomena linked to global warming that may affect animal welfare, enabling producers to implement early mitigation measures.

Policy and regulatory needs

general considerations

- **Logistical limitation:** Regulations limit production infrastructure legally to 250 m², where storage of equipment and materials, work areas, offices, and other spaces must fit. This limitation prevents business growth and scaling up production, forcing careful space management and compromising worker comfort, which in turn hinders the retention of skilled labour. The lack of scale directly affects purification facilities, which have reduced capacity to treat bivalves, limiting the volume of purified product and making exports unviable as unit costs become too high at low volumes.
- **Land availability:** Additional regulations combined with current land-use laws worsen existing difficulties. Competition with the real estate sector has raised acquisition and use costs of coastal and freshwater-adjacent areas to prohibitive levels. The recent re-naturalisation of coastal zones and surrounding estuaries hinders expansion and maintenance of production zones because inactive areas for two years are treated as renaturalized, preventing future exploitation without compensation or new permits. Since bivalve production can have two-year non-production periods, this rule contributes to sector contraction. The emergence of seagrass during this period, seen as a sign of renaturalization, could also serve as proof of low production impact.
- **Access to production units:** Most accesses and outdoor areas in Portuguese aquaculture sites are unpaved. The inability to create proper access roads and permanent infrastructure increases wear and tear on equipment used to transport products and materials, placing national aquaculture at a competitive disadvantage compared to neighbouring countries where more durable infrastructures and better access are allowed.
- **Support and insurance access:** State support for aquaculture is far lower than for other animal productions like livestock. Access to insurance is difficult due to the small size of producers and limited insurance providers in the sector. Available insurance covers are limited and do not include, for example, losses of animals due to diseases.
- **Associativism:** The national aquaculture production is mostly made up of small producers, making it difficult to defend their interests with the state and regulators. In this context, associations and cooperatives are essential to unify voices, optimize resources, and ensure effective efforts.

Challenges and opportunities for a more competitive Portuguese aquaculture

- Need for financing to create national hatcheries of aquaculture organisms, as the current scenario leads to excessive dependence on external sources.
- Need to create companies supplying materials to the production system to enable large-scale national production increase.
- Encourage implementation of infrastructures that promote energy independence for aquaculture farms to avoid vulnerability during energy shortages, such as blackouts.

artificial intelligence

- Development of a clear, transparent, and innovation-oriented regulatory framework can make Portugal a reference in the ethical and safe application of AI in aquaculture.
- Excessive bureaucracy and delays in the licensing processes for aquaculture production units.
- The current maritime spatial planning discourages national aquaculture production and generates conflicts, hindering investment and production growth.
- Creation of an accessible regulatory framework for the sustainable use of maritime space for aquaculture facilities.
- Creation of an accessible regulatory framework that promotes and simplifies the use of new ingredients, additives, and supplements in feeds.
- Creation of an accessible regulatory framework for the use of AI that ensures equitable access and strengthens food safety and animal welfare.

functional feeds

- Define specific standards to ensure the safety, efficacy, and sustainability of functional ingredients in feeds, facilitating innovation and market access to these products.
- Establish certification systems better suited for “premium” products that attest to their quality, safety, sustainability, and respect for animal welfare, helping to add value and inform consumers and producers about these products.
- Regulate incentives or financial support so that small and medium producers can adopt functional feeds, preventing increased production costs from making their use unfeasible.
- Systems that allow tracing the origin and composition of feeds, reinforcing confidence in the quality, food safety, and environmental impact of fish produced with these ingredients.
- Policies that support innovation and the development of new functional products, ensuring the entire sector keeps pace with scientific and technological advances.

food safety

- Increased regulation, while potentially ensuring greater safety and sustainability, becomes a challenge by hindering the timely entry of new operators and blocking innovation. On the other hand, less regulation may complicate the production and supply of safe, quality products at competitive/low prices, which could pose a threat to the continuity of producing companies. There is a need for regulation to allow the use of early contaminant detection systems within companies' hazard assessment frameworks, complemented by already authorized methods, enabling continuous monitoring at lower costs and ensuring more effective responses than current control systems.

animal welfare

- It is essential to create a certification system based on the product's history, which verifies origin, sustainability, and production type. These certifications should be accompanied by informative campaigns to promote consumer acceptance and trust. At the same time, it is necessary to ensure that these requirements do not compromise economic viability, especially for small producers who face challenges with the high costs associated with specific equipment, such as offshore stunning devices. Regulation should also cover the control of ingredients and additives used in feeds, to prevent the entry of lower-quality products that create unfair competition and jeopardize the national industry.
- The insufficiency of wastewater treatment plants must be addressed to prevent contamination, especially in sensitive species like bivalves.
- Regulatory barriers should be simplified to allow sustainable scale-up of production, encouraging the use of modern technologies such as AI and sensors for monitoring and predicting environmental impacts. Oversight should be standardized and constructive, supporting producers in implementing best practices.
- Exchange between academia and the production sector should be facilitated to ensure effective applied research. It is also important to fund educational campaigns and include schools to raise public awareness about the quality and sustainability of national products.
- Current regulation restricting the production of medicated mixtures to accredited entities should be reviewed to value the practical knowledge of professionals with direct production experience, without compromising safety.

Financing and R&D needs**general considerations**

- Increase the availability of renewable energy sources to make production more sustainable and resilient, reducing costs and dependence on fossil fuels.
- Research in biotechnology and circular economy helps develop solutions and technologies that promote sustainability and resource optimization, reducing waste.
- Investment in biofouling monitoring and mitigation strategies, as biofouling is already a problem for maritime sectors (notably aquaculture) and can be exacerbated by climate change (particularly water warming), with new species establishing themselves and higher recruitment/growth rates.
- Promote dialogue between producers and researchers to identify the sector's most important needs, focusing research more directly on production optimization and less on publishing detailed scientific results with less direct applicability to production. Such applied research could be conducted through direct partnerships with companies.
- Facilitate personnel exchange between science, companies, and society, enabling researchers to gain more direct knowledge of production realities.
- Projects with higher technology readiness levels (TRLs) should include economic partners to assess the economic viability of developed products and tools.
- In the Portuguese context, there is a need to differentiate aquaculture production into large-scale companies and family-run small-scale producers. R&D responses must be adapted to

these two scales of production as their needs differ. There is also a need for greater involvement of local organizations to identify these needs.

- Funding is needed for dissemination and promotion of aquaculture production, as this area is currently underfunded. Distorted reports and fake news, despite having greater impact, misinform consumers. Producers have little media presence and do not participate in public communication. Furthermore, education is deficient, with outdated content in school textbooks, creating future uninformed and negative consumers, thus hindering the transition to more conscious consumers.

artificial intelligence

- Creation of collaborative networks between companies, universities, and R&D centres, with public-private funding, focused on specific challenges in aquaculture.
- Maintenance of independent R&D networks, with transparent funding, enabling the development of AI solutions without dependence on the interests of large multinationals.
- Deepen the necessary knowledge to feed reliable predictive models, for example, correlating environmental factors with growth patterns or disease outbreaks.
- Promote continuous and specialized training in AI, combining skills in data science, aquaculture, and engineering, with the goal of developing national talent.
- Foster the development and application of computer vision technologies, essential for visual monitoring in offshore environments—for example, in biofouling detection, predator control, or fish behaviour tracking.
- Strengthen the resilience of small producers, focusing on accessible technologies and training in digital tools adapted to their reality.
- Develop public funding instruments specifically aimed at democratizing AI, ensuring that SMEs can also benefit from technological innovations.
- Development of predictive models based on artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), and advanced data analysis to improve control and efficiency in aquaculture production, promoting smarter resource management, better product traceability, and greater environmental sustainability and food safety.
- Research correlating heatwaves with animal health and disease outbreaks, to create alerts based on environmental information and allow producers to apply mitigation measures in a timely manner.

functional feeds

- Research focused on the acceptance/palatability of new feeds by the animals.
- Research focused on bioprospecting new ingredients and bioactive compounds.
- Research focused on developing technologies that allow precise and practical quantification of biomass production and waste.
- Utilization of waste/sub products rejected by aquaculture and proposals for suitable chains for their use to increase the economic and environmental sustainability of production.
- Research focused on standardizing methods to assess and validate what is understood by “functionality.”
- Greater development and promotion of consumption of species that do not require functional feeds (such as algae, bivalves, among others) as sources of protein and other nutrients for human food, to reduce dependence on species that require functional feeds.

- Promote alternatives to patent protection, avoiding short patent registrations (due to increased costs) for feed formulations, since once patents expire, products are quickly copied and marketed at lower prices.

food safety

- Research on new species, focused on authenticity and genetic improvement, could help increase resistance, quality, and traceability of products.
- Research focused on optimizing cultivation parameters for emerging species.
- Assess emerging risks that underpin effective regulations, in order to prevent threats to public health.
- Future research should align with the One Health approach principles, integrating environmental, animal, and human health, promoting sustainable practices and reducing disease and contamination risks.
- Development of new packaging to improve conservation, traceability, and product safety during transport and storage.
- The prevalence of food allergies has been increasing, making it essential to implement control measures for proper allergen management in food industries to ensure food safety for all consumers. Research should thus focus on developing detection kits for different allergens (e.g., biotoxins) in the final product.
- Research on the nutritional and toxicological impact of algae and agro-industrial by-products.

animal welfare

- Development of non-invasive preventive methods and protocols, especially prophylactic feeding and vaccines, focusing on oral administration to avoid stress caused by animal handling and chronic inflammation caused by adjuvants in injectable vaccines.
- Development of new animal welfare indicators to help prevent diseases, such as environmental sensors and measurement of metabolites and proteins related to stress and reduced immune system responsiveness, like cortisol.
- Development of environmental enrichment solutions that do not interfere with normal production functioning.
- Development of genetic selection protocols for species more resilient to climate change and diseases.
- Development of more effective stunning and slaughter methods.
- Involvement of the industry in research on emerging pathogens, such as *Lactococcus*.
- Development of strategies for controlling accessory fauna due to increased exposure to non-native species resulting from international trade and global warming.